

Electoral proportionality vs. party system concentration. The 2020 Romanian local election

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Abstract

Voter representation based on votes cast and the degree of concentration of the party system are two variables correlated with the design of the electoral system. In general, there is an inverse relationship between proportionality and concentration: when the proportionality of the electoral system increases, the concentration of the party system decreases and vice versa. This paper investigates the performance of the electoral system used in local elections in Romania, by operationalizing and measuring the two variables: proportionality and concentration. Although the elections are held under the same rules, they do not involve a unitary electoral process, but 42 distinct electoral situations, related to as many local electoral districts. There are 42 electoral competitions and basically the same number of elections. The analysis results indicate that the high magnitude PR system does not have an enhanced performance in providing both proportionality and concentration.

Keywords

electoral systems; electoral proportionality; party system concentration; local election; Romania

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Introduction

An increased proportionality, i.e. inclusive formulas and a political representation corresponding closely with the proportion of the total votes cast for each party, or a heightened concentration of the party system, i.e. restrictive formulas and a valorization of the political effects of the electoral system? It is an existing choice in the process of electoral engineering and, at the same time, a matter of intense debate in the electoral systems literature. This contradiction between proportionality and concentration is based on the inverse conditional relationship between the two variables: when the proportionality of the electoral system increases, the concentration of the party system decreases and vice versa (Carey and Hix, 2011; Raabe and Linhart, 2018).

The dichotomy of the majoritarian electoral formulas versus proportional representation (PR) formulas goes beyond the frame of a simple classification. In fact, it gives consistency to the confrontation between the two different views on the finality and the role of elections (Lijphart, 1994; Powell, 2000; Raabe and Linhart, 2018). On the one hand, the majority approach appreciates the quality of electoral systems to create functional parliamentary majorities and to ensure monochrome governments. On the other hand, proportionalists value inclusiveness and the widest possible access to the political process, orienting political actors towards negotiation and compromise, as options to ensure the functioning of composite parliamentary majorities and coalition governments.

Generally, the majoritarian electoral formulas are associated with single-party governments and PR systems with high representativeness (Duverger, 1954; Lijphart, 1994; Farrell, 2011). The attempt to combine and balance these effects has materialized in various mixed or combined electoral systems (Woldendorp, Keman and Budge, 2000; Shugart, Wattenberg, 2001; Norris, 2004). Furthermore, PR systems with a medium district magnitude “tend to have highly representative parliaments and a moderate number of parties in parliament and in government” (Carey and Hix, 2011).

Indeed, the district magnitude is an important element of the electoral system, related to proportionality and concentration (Taagepera and Shugart 1989; Lijphart 1994; Cox 1997; Gallagher and Mitchell 2005; Shugart 2005). Along with other technical factors, such as legal thresholds, allocation formulas (which is the method of translating votes into seats), and additional tiers, the district magnitude is all the more important for PR systems, which are valued primarily for their equity or fairness. PR formulas aim to allocate the seats reflecting as accurately as possible the overall distribution of votes cast for each party. In principle, no segment of society that takes part in elections and that benefits from some electoral support remains unrepresented³. In practice, the perfect proportionality between votes and seats remains a desideratum that cannot be fully achieved, but the goal of PR systems is to ensure the most accurate parliamentary representation for minority groups, assuming the effect of the fragmentation of the party system and, implicitly, the operating logic of composite parliamentary majorities and coalition governments.

Proportional representation formulas

Electoral practice has several models of the PR system, but the basic type is that of the party lists system. Party lists can be closed or open, which can influence the strategic behavior of political parties and voters, but relevant in terms of proportionality is the electoral formula, more precisely the seat allocation formula that determines how votes are translated into seats. There are two main categories

³ The relationship between political representation and electoral disproportionality is questioned by studies such as Powell Jr. and Vanberg (2000), who argue that “what matters for representation is not vote-seat proportionality, but whether the elected majority is representative of what the majority of citizens want”.

of formulas: the highest averages (D'Hondt formula, Sainte-Laguë method, modified Sainte-Laguë method) and the largest remainders (which uses a minimum quota like Hare quota or Droop quota). Given that all electoral systems, including PR, tend to overrepresent large parties to the detriment of small ones (Rae, 1967), the rules of votes-to-seats allocation also have different effects on representation and, implicitly, on proportionality. Thus, the D'Hondt method is the least favorable to small parties, while the Sainte-Laguë method or the largest remainders methods are more impartial (Lijphart, 1994; Gallagher and Mitchell, 2005).

In order to avoid fragmentation of the party system, PR electoral systems assume a deviation from proportionality by introducing electoral thresholds. Their role is that of restraining access to the Parliament and thus limiting the atomization of the legislative assembly. Their effects are of a functional nature (facilitating the creation of majorities and the formation of stable governments), but they can have an impact on the strategies of political parties and, at the same time, they can limit parliamentary representation (Lijphart, 1994, 1997; Taagepera, 1998, 2002; Moraski and Loewenberg, 1999; Gallagher and Mitchell, 2005).

The district magnitude has a similar effect, acting as an implicit barrier against small parties (Bischoff, 2004). Often considered the “decisive factor” of electoral disproportionality, the district magnitude acts in both majority and PR systems, but in different ways. In majority systems, increasing the district magnitude leads to increased electoral disproportionality and to the benefit of major parties. Instead, in PR systems it generates increased proportionality and better conditions for minor parties. In addition, as in the PR systems the variation of the magnitude is wider⁴, the impact of this factor on the electoral proportionality is stronger in the different formulas of this type⁵.

The districting arrangements of PR systems are also important. For example, additional tiers may be used to compensate for disproportionalities arising in other tiers. Also, there can be PR systems with numerous local multi-member districts and with an additional national district, whose purpose is to compensate for the deviation from proportionality that may arise at the level of the local districts (Colomer, 2004; Raabe and Linhart, 2018). In this case, we have “two-tier compensatory member electoral systems” (Elklit and Roberts, 1996) that use different formulas to allocate different portions of seats.

All these technical elements that have a rich literature represent just as many variables, which together with factors external to electoral systems, such as the size of the electoral body to be elected, the electoral participation, the number of electoral competitors, or the relations between parties, have an impact on proportionality and on the outcomes of the electoral system.

Hypotheses and analysis tools

Using a PR system with a large and very large district magnitude (over 30, for example) should provide high levels of proportionality and fragmentation (low concentration of the party system). If the method for seat allocation is more favorable to large parties (for example, a combination of the simple quota and the largest remainder method), proportionality could be affected, but a large district magnitude could compensate for this biasing effect. If in a number of distinct electoral districts where the PR system is used all technical elements are constant (the district magnitude is high in all cases, the legal

⁴ Disproportionality decreases as one moves from lower to higher magnitudes.

⁵ Not only the district magnitude, but also their number has an impact on proportionality, since the territorial homogeneity, i.e. the distribution of party voters at the administrative-territorial level, is “strongly influenced by the number of territorial units that are taken into account” (Bochsler, 2010).

electoral threshold and the electoral formula are the same everywhere), we can expect the election results to be relatively compact, in the sense of increased convergence or high homogeneity, both from the perspective of proportionality and concentration.

We test these hypotheses in the case of the 2000 Romanian local elections, specifically the election of county councilors and the general council of Bucharest. The Romanian counties correspond to the NUTS III level of the European Union nomenclature, being the largest administrative-territorial units mentioned in the Constitution. From a political and electoral point of view, the counties are a reflection and, at the same time, a predictor of the competition at the national level. From a methodological point of view, the level of proportionality and the degree of concentration of the party system are quantified and measured by two of the most used indices in electoral system research. One of them is Gallagher's index for measuring the level of proportionality (Gallagher, 1991):

$$G = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2} \sum (S_p - V_p)^2},$$

where S_p denotes the seat share of a party p and V_p its vote share. When it comes to the concentration of the party system, we use the index proposed by Laakso and Taagepera based on parliamentary seat distributions – the effective number of parties (Laakso and Taagepera, 1979):

$$N = 1 / \sum S_p^2.$$

The pattern of Romanian local elections

Romanian local elections take place at three levels, corresponding to the administrative-territorial units of the country: communes, cities, and counties. The counties have, on average, almost 450,000 inhabitants, but their population varies from just over 210,000 (Covasna) to almost 800,000 inhabitants (Iași). The capital of the country, Bucharest, the country's largest city (around 1,900,000 inhabitants), is a distinct administrative-territorial unit, but it is associated with the counties from an electoral point of view. Therefore, local elections take place in 41+1 electoral units, which we will generically call counties.

Citizens elect local government bodies, both legislative – the County Councils (CC), and the General Council, in Bucharest – and executive – the Presidents of the County Councils, and the General Mayor of Bucharest. County Councils are collegial bodies elected for four-year terms, with the role of coordinating the activity of communes and cities, in order to provide public services. They consist of a variable number of councilors, depending on the population they represent. The President of the CC is responsible for the proper functioning of the county administration and represents the county in relations with citizens and other public authorities.

The electoral formula used for the election of the county council members belongs to the PR system, i.e. closed list PR system. Each county, including Bucharest, constitutes a multi-member electoral district. Among the 41+1 counties, 11 have a magnitude of 30, 13 have a magnitude of 32, nine have 34 seats, eight of them have 36 seats, and the General Council of Bucharest has 55 seats. The allocation of these seats is carried out on the basis of the simple electoral quota and the largest remainder method, for the electoral competitors who meet the electoral threshold condition⁶. In principle, the (relatively) high average magnitude favors the increase of electoral proportionality, but the methods of allocating seats have the opposite effect (Rae, 1967; Lijphart, 1990; Martin, 1997).

⁶ For political parties, the threshold is 5% of the total number of valid votes in the district. For political or electoral alliances, 2% shall be added to the 5% threshold for the second member of the alliance. For alliances with at least 3 members, the electoral threshold is 8%.

The eight rounds of local elections organized after the collapse of the communist regime highlight the stability of the proportional electoral mechanism used for the election of County Councils. With the exception of the first election (1992), when the county councilors were elected indirectly, by a body of voters formed by all the members of the local councils in the county, the closed list PR system which combines the simple electoral quota and the largest remainder method was employed for all subsequent editions of the election of county councilors, without systemic changes. The only significant update was the introduction of the electoral threshold, starting with the 2004 elections.

As for the method of electing the President of the County Council, it has undergone a few changes over time. Between 1992 and 2004, and in 2016, the president of the CC was elected indirectly, from among the county councilors. In 2008, 2012 and 2020, the president was elected directly by the citizens who were entitled to vote in the 41+1 electoral units. The direct elections used the plurality electoral formula (“first past the post” allocation rules), the tendency of which is to affect the representativeness of the elected official.

It is also worth noting the constant organization of local elections a few months before the parliamentary elections, a fact that amplified the stake and political relevance of the former. Effectively, the results of the competition at the county level functioned as a “litmus paper” for national elections (Radu and Buti, 2015) or as a “barometer of the relations between the main political parties” (Radu, 2012), outlining the electoral axes, highlighting certain trends, providing strategic information for electoral competitors and guiding voting options for the electorate. This transformed the local elections “into a ‘subspecies’ of second-order elections” (Dragoman and Zamfira, 2018).

Like parliamentary elections, local elections are centralized, in the sense that their regulation and organization is carried out at the national level. The law on local elections requires a single electoral formula (the same electoral formula) for all counties, and electoral management falls to the Central Electoral Bureau. However, functionally there are distinct electoral processes in each of the 41+1 electoral units. They are distinct primarily by the level of political participation. Despite having lists of candidates, usually in all counties, the national/major parties often resort to local alliances, different from one county to another. Therefore, parties opt for different electoral strategies, for alliances and associative formulas adapted to county context, which means that electoral competitors are not always the same in all constituencies. Local political parties, which particularize the competition, as well as other specific political and socio-economic factors also compound the process. Thus, the number of electoral competitors varies from county to county. More importantly, the procedures for counting votes and allocating seats are carried out at the local level, by the electoral body in each county – the County Electoral Bureau. Therefore, local elections do not constitute a national/unitary electoral process, but 42 distinct electoral situations, 42 electoral competitions and as many elections.

The 2020 local elections

The last local elections were held in atypical conditions. Originally scheduled for June of 2020, the elections were postponed to September, due to the Covid-19 pandemic. The unfolding of the electoral campaign and of the entire electoral process was under restrictions and sanitary safety measures, adopted as part of the state of alert at the national level. Even so, 69 political parties, political alliances, electoral alliances, and organizations of citizens belonging to national minorities entered the competition for county councils. Thirty of them (43.48%) obtained councilor seats. However, the elections were dominated by the major parties, with national representation.

At the national level, the electoral statistics show the following. The 7,758,055 voters present at the polls (46.63%) sent between two and six electoral competitors to the county councils. More than half of the valid votes (53.08%), as well as the seats of county councilors (62.38%) were won by the two major parties, in polar positions: the National Liberal Party (PNL) and the Social Democratic Party (PSD).

Overall, the results of the elections for the county councils gave the victory to PNL (see Appendix B), considering both the number of votes received at the national level (30.76%) and the number of seats obtained (35.37%). PSD was in second place with 22.32% of the votes cast and 27.01% of the seats. The electoral hierarchy is completed by a group of three parliamentary political formations that obtained between 5% and 7% of the votes (USR PLUS Alliance, People's Movement Party – PMP, the Democratic Alliance of Hungarians in Romania – UDMR), two other parliamentary parties with results between 2% and 5% (Pro Romania Party, the Alliance of Liberals and Democrats – ALDE), a group that obtained between 1% and 2% of the votes cast, formed by an extra-parliamentary party (the Romanian Ecologist Party – PER) and four distinct alliances established at the county level through various associative formulas of the parliamentary parties, and a group with subunit percentages which includes various local political alliances, a local political party, a political organization of ethnic Germans and a parliamentary formation.

The two major rival parties shared, alone or in various alliances, the first places in the electoral hierarchy in 38 electoral districts, representing 90.48% of the total of 41+1. PNL won the elections in 17 counties and in another its victory was possible thanks to the alliance with USR PLUS. PSD won the elections in 19 counties and the municipality of Bucharest, in four of them being allied with minor parties (ALDE, Pro Romania and the Humanist Power Party – PPU). The other four constituencies went to UDMR, which dominates, from an electoral point of view, the counties with a Hungarian population. It should be noted that in seven constituencies the elections were won with a majority vote: three of them went to PNL (Alba, Bihor, Giurgiu), two to PSD (Buzău, Olt) and two to UDMR (Covasna, Harghita).

In the case of county council presidents, the competition was also dominated by the two major national parties (PNL and PSD), which, together with UDMR, shared the 41 seats (see Appendix B). Thus, PSD candidates won the competition in 16 electoral districts, plus other four victories alongside minor parties, resulting in a total of 20 seats. For its part, PNL obtained 17 presidents of county councils, in two cases being allied with USR PLUS. Finally, UDMR won four seats. Of all the seats of county council president, nine (21.95%) were obtained with a majority vote, as follows: PSD - four (Bistrița-Năsăud, Brăila, Buzău, Olt), PNL - three (Alba, Bihor, Cluj) and UDMR - two (Covasna, Harghita). The mandate of General Mayor of Bucharest was won by an independent, supported by PNL and USR PLUS.

When the results of the elections for the county councils – an electoral competition with an important political dimension – are compared against the results of the election of county council presidents – a competition in which the candidate's imagological profile and personality may count more than his political affiliation – a monotony of the political vote results. Thus, in 37 constituencies (88.10% of the total of 41+1⁷) there is monotony indicating that the plurality of voters (and in some cases the majority of them) preferred the same political actor both for the county council and for the head of this institution. Therefore, a uniform pattern of electoral behavior can be observed in the case of county wide elections. Only in five constituencies (11.90%) did the voters divide the power between different political actors (Hunedoara, Teleorman, Tulcea, Vrancea, and Bucharest).

⁷ In the particular case of the Bucharest constituency, the General Council, assimilated to the county councils, respectively the General Mayor, assimilated to the presidents of the county councils, was considered.

Electoral disproportionality – G index

The unitary regulation of the 42 distinct electoral competitions, respectively the practice of the same electoral system, a PR type electoral system with large district magnitudes, creates the expectation of a low degree of dispersion of electoral disproportionality. With an average of 6.21%, the value of the G index varies, however, quite a lot, from 1.73% to 9.59% (see Appendix A), which means that the ratio between the most proportional and the most disproportionate county is five to one. At the same time, the distribution of the 42 constituencies according to the degree of electoral disproportionality compared to the average of the G index is quite balanced. Thus, 19 counties plus Bucharest have disproportionality values below the average, and in 22 counties the value of this indicator is higher than the average.

Beyond the electoral threshold value, the differences in terms of proportionality are given by the fragmentation of the electoral offer (number of electoral competitors) and the concentration or dispersion of votes, more precisely the wasted votes (politically unrepresented votes). In the electoral districts with good PR electoral system performance (low values of the G index), the number of electoral competitors, the number of parties that do not reach the electoral threshold, as well as the percentage of wasted votes are lower compared to those in counties with a high degree of electoral disproportionality. For example, in the Prahova constituency, where the PR system provides the highest proportionality, there were five electoral competitors and all of them obtained seats in the county council. The 36 seats were allocated to three political parties and two electoral alliances, and the difference between the percentage of votes and the percentage of seats is not very large: two of the competitors, the one in first place and the one ranked fourth, benefited from a slight over-representation (+1.40% for PNL USR PLUS Alliance, respectively +1.24% for ALDE), and the other three were slightly under-represented (-1.03% for Prahova Alliance, -1.06% for PMP and -0.54% for Prahova in Action Party).

At the opposite end is the constituency of Galați, with the highest degree of electoral disproportionality. Here, 15 political formations and independent candidates entered the competition, and the 34 seats were allocated to four of them. Basically, 11 competitors, who attracted 17.66% of the votes, did not reach the electoral threshold. In this case, all the electoral competitors who got seats were over-represented, the major parties being clearly advantaged over the minor ones: the first ranked party (PSD) has a bonus (the percentage difference between votes and seats) of +10.28%, the second-placed party (PNL) has a deviation from proportionality of +8.21%, the one in the third place (PMP) has +3.09%, and the last ranked (ALDE) has a bonus of +0.30%.

Party system fragmentation – N index

In general, PR systems are associated with high levels of the effective number of parties, an indicator that is moderated by specific political factors and technical elements or “mathematical tools” (Raabe and Linhart, 2018) of the electoral system, such as the electoral threshold or the district magnitude. Analyzed from this perspective, the 42 electoral constituencies oscillate between a minimum level of the N index of 1.78% and a maximum of 3.71% (see Appendix A), the ratio between the most concentrated and the least concentrated party system being two to one. The arithmetic average of 2.69% indicates a concentration level of the party system specific rather to majoritarian electoral systems or to mixed-member proportional (MMP) type. It does not suggest the existence of a multi-party system, but of a two-and-a-half-party system or, upon a closer look at the electoral results in each county, of a bipolarized multi-party system. Although there are three constituencies (Giurgiu, Olt,

Teleorman) where the seats of county councilors were divided between two parties (PNL and PSD) and another 11 counties where three competitors entered the county council, in the vast majority of constituencies (66.7%) the actual number of parties is between four and six. In general, the party system is structured on two axes, a central axis, on which we find the two major parties (PSD and PNL) and a secondary axis, made up of two to four small parties.

The distribution compared to the average of the effective number of parties of the 42 constituencies is (as in the case of the G index) quite balanced. Thus, 22 counties have values of the N index lower than the average, and in 19 counties plus Bucharest this indicator is above the average. In the counties with the lowest values of the effective number of parties, under two (Covasna, Olt, Giurgiu), the electoral competition is unbalanced with the distance between the first two competitors being significant. Also, in these electoral districts, the elections were won with a majority vote, and in two of them, the county council has only two political parties as political composition. At the opposite end are the counties with low levels of party system concentration (Maramureş, Neamţ, Constanţa). These are counties where the party system and the vote (voters' electoral options) are more dispersed, and the electoral competition is more balanced.

The diagram of Romanian local districts

Generally, PR systems are recognized for low values of the G-index and for increased levels of party system fragmentation (high values of the N-index). Proportionality and concentration are two variables that PR systems fail to make compatible, but which can coexist even when the technical components of the electoral system, such as the district magnitude or the electoral threshold, are relatively constant. Thus, the combination of the two dimensions in the case of the 41 county constituencies and the Bucharest municipality constituency, reveals a picture that, on the one hand, is balanced, and on the other hand, is contrary to what we would have expected.

The intersection of the medians of the two indices groups the electoral districts into four categories (see Figure 1):

- I. proportional and concentrated (performing in both dimensions, $Q < 6.21$ and $N < 2.69$ – lower left quadrant)
- II. disproportionate and fragmented (poor performance in both dimensions, $Q > 6.21$ and $N > 2.69$ – upper right quadrant)
- III. proportional but fragmented ($Q < 6.21$ and $N > 2.69$ – upper left quadrant)
- IV. disproportionate and concentrated ($Q > 6.21$ and $N < 2.69$ – lower right quadrant)

As suggested by Figure 1, the four categories are relatively balanced, in the sense that two of them, namely the best performing (proportional and concentrated) and the least performing (disproportionate and fragmented), each contain nine electoral units (constituencies), the proportional but fragmented category contains 11 cases, and the disproportionate and concentrated category has 13 cases.

In the first category, the values of the G index are between 2.24 (Harghita) and 6.08 (Buzău), and the N index varies between 2.02 (Buzău) and 2.69 (Argeş). In the second category, the degree of electoral disproportionality varies between 6.24 (Iaşi) and 8.60 (Ialomiţa), and the concentration of the party system has values between 2.71 (Ialomiţa) and 3.71 (Maramureş). The third category contains electoral districts where the G index varies between 1.73 (Prahova, Vaslui) and 5.57 (Sălaj), and the N index varies between 2.93 (Dolj) and 3.57 (Neamţ). The fourth category contains electoral districts with degrees of disproportionality in the range from 6.63 (Bistriţa-Năsăud) to 9.06 (Covasna) and with party system concentration values between 1.78 (Covasna) and 2.63 (Sibiu).

Figure 1. Electoral proportionality vs. party system concentration – 42 Romanian electoral districts

Source: Own elaboration.

At the same time, novel and somewhat unspecific for a PR system, the category with the most electoral districts is the one where the G index has high values and the N index has low values, i.e. the fourth category. In other words, in these constituencies, elections are the most disproportionate and they lead to the most concentrated party systems.

In the case of constituencies performing in both dimensions, Harghita has the highest proportionality ($G=2.24$), and Buzău the most concentrated party system ($N=2.02$). It should be noted that Harghita is one of the constituencies with the smallest electoral magnitude and in which five electoral competitors shared the 30 seats of the county council. At the same time, Harghita is an electoral stronghold for the UDMR which, together with the other political organizations of ethnic Hungarians gathered for the 2020 elections in the Transylvanian Hungarian Alliance, gained 23 seats (76.67%) and mobilized 74% of the votes. Even in the case of Buzău, the district magnitude is not very high (compared to the other constituencies), the 32 seats being contested by five electoral competitors. Among them, three managed to enter the county council, with an electoral alliance consisting of two parties taking first place. Both in Harghita and in Buzău, an electoral competitor – UDMR, respectively PSD-Pro Buzău Alliance – obtained the majority of votes and seats.

Among the nine constituencies with a double negative performance, the most proportional is Iasi, and the most concentrated is Ialomița. Iasi is a large electoral district, with 36 seats in the county council. Twelve political actors competed here, four of them managed to win seats. In contrast, Ialomița has a small district magnitude (compared to the other constituencies). Eleven political actors competed for the 30 seats, three of them managed to enter the county council. In both electoral districts, the competition was dominated by the main national parties, PNL and PSD.

Of the proportional but fragmented constituencies, Prahova stands out, which is the most proportional, but also the most concentrated constituency in this category. Moreover, in Prahova, the electoral system produces the most proportional results in the entire country, more precisely among all 41 electoral districts plus Bucharest. This is one of the large constituencies with 36 seats. Here, five political actors entered the electoral competition and all of them managed to get seats as county councilors. The protagonists were two electoral alliances formed around the rival parties PNL and PSD - the PNL USR PLUS Alliance, respectively the Alliance for Prahova. The two political and electoral blocs together obtained 77.78% of the votes cast and the same percentage of the total number of seats.

The category of electoral districts where the PR system produces disproportionate results and is associated with a concentrated party system is the largest. Among the 13 constituencies, the most proportional is Bistrița-Năsăud, and the most concentrated is Covasna. In Bistrița-Năsăud, 11 political actors competed for the 30 county councilor seats. Of these, three managed to enter the county council. The competition revolved around PNL and PSD, the latter running in the elections, along with two other political parties, in the Alliance for Bistrița-Năsăud. Regarding Covasna, which has the most concentrated party system among all 42 electoral districts, it follows the same electoral pattern as Harghita, a constituency in the category of those with a double performance. The county is politically and electorally dominated by the UDMR, which obtained the majority of votes and 73.33% of the 30 seats. Here, out of the nine political organizations that registered in the elections, four managed to get seats as county councilors.

Conclusions

A first finding from our analysis is that the data partially confirm the effects of the various technical variables of the proportional electoral system on disproportionality and concentration. Even if all 42 constituencies have a high district magnitude (between 30 and 36/55), one can distinguish between 30-32-member districts and 34-36-member districts. From this point of view, as expected, most high-magnitude districts (34 and 36) are in the category of double performance as well as proportional but fragmented. Thus, out of the nine 34-member districts, three are in the first category, and two in the third category. Also, out of the eight electoral districts with 36 seats for county councilors, five are in the third category. On the other hand, out of the 24 electoral districts with 30 and 32 seats, 15 are in categories two and four, i.e. those with the lowest electoral proportionality.

Beyond this grouping of constituencies according to electoral magnitude to highlight differences between the four categories, all 42 electoral units in Romania have (very) high district magnitudes. From this perspective, our first hypothesis – that the use of a PR system with large and very large district magnitude should provide high levels of proportionality and fragmentation (low concentration of the party system) – is only partially confirmed. This is because only 11 constituencies (26.2%) have proportional results and a fragmented party system, thus bringing the two variables together. In other words, most of the electoral districts (20, i.e. 47.6%) are either only proportional (categories one and three) or only fragmented (categories two and three) as a party system (20). We also add that the most consistent category (with the most electoral districts, precisely 13, i.e. 31%) is category four, i.e. the one with disproportionate elections and concentrated party systems.

Regarding the second hypothesis – if the seats allocation method is more favorable to large parties (as is the case with the Romanian combination of the simple quota and the largest remainder method), proportionality could be affected, but a large district magnitude could compensate for this biasing effect –, the Romanian electoral reality leads to nuanced conclusions. In this case, another technical factor, that of the actual number of parties, only partially confirms the expectation that in

electoral districts with a high level of electoral proportionality, the number of electoral competitors who land seats is higher. Remember that in the case of the 42 constituencies, the actual number of parties varies between two and five. Among those with five parties in the county council, 11 are in categories two and especially three, i.e. the one with low performance in both dimensions, respectively the one with cases of proportionality, but fragmentation. Also, the only constituencies (three of them) in which the seats of county councilors were shared by two electoral competitors all fall in the fourth category, the one with high disproportionality and concentration of the party system. Moreover, ten of the 11 constituencies where the actual number of parties is three are, equally divided, in categories one and four, i.e. those containing cases of concentration of the party system.

To narrow and refine the conclusion regarding the partial validation of the second hypothesis, attention must be turned to categories one and three, which contain electoral districts with the most proportional results. Thus, in the third category are the most electoral districts with maximum magnitude (36) – five districts (out of a total of 11). For all this, the actual number of parties is five. Also, in this category there are two electoral districts with magnitude 34. In both of them, the actual number of parties is five. At the same time, category three includes the exceptional case of Bucharest, the electoral district with the largest magnitude (55). According to our hypothesis, in this constituency, we would have expected the actual number of parties to be greater than or equal to five. Here, however, only four political parties entered the local/municipal legislative forum.

The hypothesis is also nuanced by the specificity of category one, in which the highest district magnitude is 34. There are three electoral districts of this type (out of a total of nine), one of which has four parties in the county council and two with three parties each. There is also a constituency where the actual number of parties is five, but this has the lowest magnitude (30). In most of the electoral districts (five) in this category, the seats were shared between three parties.

In the case of the third hypothesis – if in a number of distinct electoral districts where the PR system is used, all technical elements are constant (the district magnitude is high in all cases, the legal electoral threshold and the electoral formula are the same everywhere), we can expect the election results to be relatively compact, in the sense of increased convergence or high homogeneity, both from the perspective of proportionality and concentration –, the data offer it support: based on the two measured indices, the 42 electoral districts are quite homogeneous and convergent.

With a mean G-index of 6.21 and a standard deviation of 2.08, the electoral districts are quite concentrated, with a coefficient of variation (CV) of 0.334. Individual G-index values are not widely dispersed relative to the average value. The N index reveals an even greater convergence of values and an increased uniformity of the electoral districts. With an average N index of 2.69 and a standard deviation of 0.48, the 42 Romanian electoral districts have a high degree of homogeneity (CV = 0.177).

Held under a high-magnitude PR electoral system, Romanian local elections do not lead to an excessive fragmentation of the party system, but neither do they produce very proportional results. Ordered into four categories based on the two dimensions – electoral proportionality and party concentration –, the 41+1 local electoral districts are fairly balanced, but, from a quantitative point of view, the best performers (proportional and concentrated) are minority and equal to the least performing (disproportionate and fragmented). Additionally, even those that best reflect the classic effects of the PR system (proportional but fragmented) do not have a dominant status, being outranked by disproportionate and concentrated districts. The dominance of national parties, the bipolar feature of the party system, as well as the fragmented nature of local elections, with unitary rules and also particular electoral situations, specific to each electoral district, are explanatory factors of the picture resulting from the Romanian local elections in 2020.

Appendix A – The degree of electoral disproportionality and the effective number of parties

Electoral district	G index	N index
Alba	6.78	2.43
Arad	4.24	3.01
Argeş	4.69	2.69
Bacău	4.69	3.00
Bihor	5.74	2.08
Bistriţa-Năsăud	6.63	2.53
Botoşani	5.57	2.68
Braşov	8.37	2.98
Brăila	8.06	2.26
Bucureşti	5.39	3.36
Buzău	6.08	2.02
Caraş-Severin	7.28	2.42
Călăraşi	5.57	2.26
Cluj	4.90	2.95
Constanţa	5.48	3.52
Covasna	9.06	1.78
Dâmboviţa	5.39	2.44
Dolj	4.69	2.93
Galaţi	9.59	2.59
Giurgiu	8.31	1.92
Gorj	6.78	2.63
Harghita	2.24	2.28
Hunedoara	7.42	2.83
Ialomiţa	8.60	2.71
Iaşi	6.24	2.99
Ilfov	3.74	3.14
Maramureş	6.24	3.71
Mehedinţi	3.74	2.54
Mureş	8.25	2.96
Neamţ	2.00	3.57
Olt	8.43	1.82
Prahova	1.73	3.00
Satu Mare	7.42	2.89
Sălaj	5.57	3.29
Sibiu	7.48	2.63
Suceava	7.81	2.50
Teleorman	8.94	1.99
Timiş	8.37	3.13
Tulcea	7.62	2.76
Vaslui	1.73	3.19
Vâlcea	8.31	2.36
Vrancea	5.57	2.26
Average	6.21	2.69

Appendix B – 2020 votes and seats by electoral competitors

Electoral competitor	No. Votes	% Voted	No. Seats	% Seats
County Councils:				
PNL	2,212,904	30.76	474	35.37
PSD	1,605,721	22.32	362	27.01
Alianța USR PLUS	478,659	6.65	65	4.85
PMP	423,147	5.88	67	5.00
UDMR	379,924	5.28	92	6.87
Pro Romania	356,030	4.95	56	4.18
ALDE	209,411	2.91	15	1.12
Alianța PNL USR PLUS	131,179	1.82	17	1.27
Alianța electorală PSD+ALDE Dolj	103,318	1.44	16	1.19
Alianța PSD-Pro Buzău	103,227	1.43	21	1.57
PER	101,087	1.41	5	0.37
Alianța pentru Prahova	90,442	1.26	11	0.82
Alianța pentru modernizarea Neamțului 2020	65,179	0.91	13	0.97
PSD-ALDE-PNȚCD-ADER	62,007	0.86	10	0.75
Alianța PNL-USR-PLUS	58,610	0.81	15	1.12
Alianța PNL-USR-PLUS	61,621	0.86	11	0.82
Alianța pentru Bistrița-Năsăud	50,572	0.70	14	1.04
Pro Caraș-Severin	32,680	0.45	10	0.75
Alianța PNL-UDMR-PNȚCD	30,907	0.43	7	0.52
Alianța PNL-USR Călărași	46,932	0.65	13	0.97
Alianța electorală Coaliția pentru Maramureș CMM	46,197	0.64	10	0.75
Alianța PSD-PPU (SL)	38,458	0.53	7	0.52
Alianța Maghiară din Transilvania	22,875	0.32	7	0.52
FDGR	24,333	0.34	5	0.37
Alianța Social Liberală	23,487	0.33	5	0.37
Platforma Social-Liberal Creștină	16,029	0.22	3	0.22
Partidul Oamenilor Liberi	14,123	0.20	2	0.15
USR	9,819	0.14	2	0.15
Partidul Prahova în Acțiune	17,464	0.24	2	0.15
Alianța U.S.R. PLUS	12,140	0.17	3	0.22
County Council presidents:				
PNL	2,261,157	31.07	15	36.58
PSD	1,163,399	22.86	16	39.02
UDMR	366,480	5.04	4	9.76
Alianța PNL USR PLUS	181,822	2.50	1	2.44
Alianța electorală PSD+ALDE Dolj	111,317	1.53	1	2.44
Alianța PSD-Pro Buzău	103,412	1.38	1	2.44
Alianța pentru modernizarea Neamțului 2020	77,208	1.06	1	2.44
Alianța pentru Bistrița-Năsăud	66,039	0.91	1	2.44
Alianța PNL-USR-PLUS	65,637	0.90	1	2.44
Total (registered) voters			16,638,493	
Total votes			7,758,055	
Turnout		46.63%		
Total seats – county councils			1,340	
Total seats – county councils presidents			41	

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